

LEAKAGE DAMAGE AND FAILURE OF GLASS-FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITE TUBULAR VESSELS UNDER COMBINED INTERNAL PRESSURE AND AXIAL LOADING

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ABSTRACT

Corrosion resistance and high specific stiffness and strength have made filament-wound fiber reinforced polymer-matrix composites an important class of engineering materials for a wide range of chemical and petroleum industry applications. In this paper multiaxial deformations and leakage failure as well as the associated failure mechanisms are studied for commonly used glass-fiber reinforced composite tubular vessels subjected to internal pressure and axial loading. The two composite vessels considered in this study contained typical lamina lay-ups of $[(\pm 55^\circ)]_2$ and $[(\pm 66^\circ)_2/(0^\circ)_2/(\pm 66^\circ)_3/0^\circ]_s$. In the experimental program, a multiaxial testing system was used for simulating combined internal pressure and axial tension/compression with both proportional and nonproportional loading paths. The leakage failure of the vessels was defined as the damage state in which microcracks coalesce to form a through-the-thickness crack while structural integrity was still retained. Both of the composite vessels exhibited highly distorted multiaxial leakage failure envelopes. Detailed microscopy studies revealed the fundamental characteristics of damage in the composite vessels under proportional and nonproportional loading.

INTRODUCTION

Filament-wound fiber reinforced polymer-matrix composites have been used extensively in chemical, petroleum, and processing industries. Recent applications of the glass-fiber reinforced composite tubular vessels in high-pressure and high-axial loading operations have led to serious concerns about their functional and structural load bearing behavior. In many important engineering components, the functional failure of a pressurized composite vessel in the form of leakage of containing fluid is more critical than the loss of structural load bearing in design and performance considerations of the composites.

The leakage failure of a filament-wound fiber composite vessels, subjected to a combined internal pressure and axial loading, is commonly viewed as a result of progressive damage in the form of microcracking and the coalescence of the microcracks to form a through-the-thickness crack path prior to the complete loss of structural load bearing capability. Obviously, the nature of the problem is very complicated, as it involves not only the complex evolution, i.e., the initiation and growth, of various damage forms in the composite but also the heterogeneous microstructure of an anisotropic layered fiber composite. In addition, the unknown effects of complex multiaxial loading modes with almost unlimited combinations of stress (or strain) biaxiality ratios and load paths have led to very limited understanding of the leakage behavior of composite vessels. Quantitative relationships among the leakage failure parameters, the damage state in the material, composite lamination variables, and the multiaxial loading need to be established.

Extensive research has been reported [1,2] on load bearing failure of thin-wall composite laminate vessels subjected to combined internal pressure and axial loads. Mechanical properties of unidirectional graphite/epoxy [3] and glass/epoxy composites [4-8] were studied from hoop-wound composite tubes. Most experimental studies in the literature on composite vessels have focused on structural failure whereas the important issue of progressive material damage leading to leakage failure has been less addressed. In an early paper by Ecknold, et al.[8], a structural failure envelope has been constructed for filament-wound E-glass/polyester vessels with different ply orientations subjected to various combinations of internal pressure and axial loads. Similar analyses have also been conducted for carbon/epoxy [9] and Kevlar/epoxy [10] composite vessels. Experimental research on leakage and structural failure envelopes for lined and unlined filament wound E-glass/epoxy [11] composite vessels subjected to biaxial loads has been reported. The unlined vessels leaked first while the lined vessels fractured catastrophically at significantly higher loading magnitude. Owing to the rapid development of composite vessels for low and high pressure applications, limited leakage experiments have also been conducted on E-glass/polyester [12] and E-glass/epoxy [13] composite laminate vessels.

In this paper, an experimental study is reported to provide information on the leakage failure of glass-fiber reinforced epoxy composite vessels subjected to various combinations of internal pressure and axial loading. Load-deformation behavior of the composites under multiaxial loading is obtained and associated leakage failure mechanisms are discussed. Failure envelopes of the multiaxial loading induced leakage for two composite systems are presented. The important issues of stress biaxiality ratio and load path effects on the composite leakage behavior are addressed.

MATERIALS, AND SPECIMEN DESIGN AND PREPARATION

Table 1 summarizes the lay-up sequence and dimensions of filament-wound E-glass fiber reinforced epoxy composite tubular vessels used in this study.

Table 1: Lay-up sequence and geometry of specimens used in the multiaxial experiments

Lay-up	$[(\pm 55^\circ)]_2$	$[(\pm 66^\circ)_2/(0^\circ)_2/(\pm 66^\circ)_3/0^\circ]_5$
Inner Diameter	2.24"	1.94"
Outer Diameter	2.40"	2.36"
Tab Material	Woven fabric	E-Glass/Epoxy

Various specimen gripping configurations have been evaluated using combined finite element and composite mechanics approaches to ensure a uniform biaxial stress state in the gage section of the specimen. A design using a low stiffness material around the gripping and end-plug seal regions has been shown to reduce stress concentrations significantly [14]. The grip design procedure recognized the competition among several failure modes and minimized tab failure during multiaxial loading. The specimen tabs were machined to the exact grip dimensions (with 5° taper angle and 3.34 largest diameter) while the gage section (middle 4" section) was kept at as-received condition. The length of the specimens were 15".

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Multiaxial testing system

A comprehensive experimental program was conducted to study multiaxial deformation, leakage and structural failure of filament-wound composite tubular vessels. The experimental system was devised to simulate both proportional and nonproportional combinations of tension, torsion, and internal/external pressure loading.

The facilities consisted of two closed-loop loading systems, one for internal pressure and one for axial/rotational loading (Fig. 1). Internal pressure was provided by a single stroke oil-to-water pressure intensifier with a design pressure of 10000 psi. The internal pressure loop was controlled by an analog controller, which measured piston displacement through an LVDT attached to the intensifier piston and pressure through a pressure transducer attached to the intensifier outlet. The second loop for axial/rotational loading consisted of a servohydraulic axial/torsion test frame with capacity of up to ± 56 kips for axial loads and torsion up to ± 22 kip-in in user-defined combinations. The axial/rotational loop was controlled by a biaxial digital control system which read load from the load cell and axial/rotational displacement from the actuator.

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of the triaxial experimental system

Data acquisition systems

The system recorded axial load, torque, and position from the servohydraulic machine; axial and shear strains from the multiaxial extensometer and strain gages; and pressure and piston displacement from the pressure intensifier. The signals were processed through a combination of eight quarter-and-half Wheatstone bridges. Real-time data acquisition and storage was achieved by using a commercially available A/D board.

Leakage measurement techniques

Due to experimental difficulties, definitions of leakage and associated leakage failure criteria have remained ambiguous in the literature. The leakage process of the specimens during an experiment was monitored with the aid of two leakage detection systems: the first system monitored the rate of fluid loss through the vessel walls and the second system used a conductive metal mesh to monitor fluid leakage. These systems allowed us to establish a well-defined leakage failure criteria.

Experimental procedure

Combined axial load and internal pressure experiments were conducted in load/pressure controlled mode up to leakage failure. The loading rate during the multiaxial experiments was defined as $\sigma_{av} = 20$ psi/sec, where $\sigma_{av} = (\sigma_{\theta}^2 + \sigma_{ax}^2)^{1/2}$ with σ_{θ} and σ_{ax} being hoop and axial stresses, respectively. Axial and hoop deformations were recorded by four strain gages mounted in the gage section of the specimen; two along the axis of the specimen with 180° apart and the other two perpendicular to the loading axis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Load-deformation characteristics of selected loading cases

Typical global load deformation responses of two composite vessels with different laminate lay-ups subjected to different biaxial loads are shown in Figs. 2 and 3. The strains measured from the two gages are generally compared well. The load-deformation responses were typically linear at a small magnitude of an applied load, followed by a "kink" and increased noise in strain signals with an increasing load. The latter phenomenon could be indicative of damage in the form of individual ply cracking or delamination.

Figure 2: Load-deformation response of an E-glass/epoxy specimen with $[(\pm 66^\circ)_2 / (0^\circ)_2 / (\pm 66^\circ)_3 / (0^\circ)]_s$ lamina lay-up subjected to a combined internal pressure and axial loading.

Figure 3: Load-deformation response of an E-glass/epoxy specimen with $[(\pm 55^{\circ})_2]$ lamina lay-up subjected to a combined internal pressure and axial loading.

Multiaxial leakage failure envelope of glass/epoxy composite tubular vessels

Multiaxial leakage failure envelopes obtained for the two composite vessels are presented in Fig. 4. Some scatter in leakage failure loads for the $[(\pm 66^{\circ})_2/(0^{\circ})_2/(\pm 66^{\circ})_3/0^{\circ}]_s$ case is noted, especially for biaxial ratios with a high hoop stress component. This may be attributed to the nonuniformity in the geometry of the specimens. Note that the leakage envelope follows a concave shape. The composite vessels with $[(\pm 55^{\circ})_2]$ lay-up sequence exhibited higher strength under biaxial loading as compared to the uniaxial (hoop or axial only) strength.

Figure 4: Multiaxial leakage failure envelope of E-glass/epoxy composite tubular vessels a) $[(\pm 55^{\circ})_2]$ lamina lay-up and b) $[(\pm 66^{\circ})_2/(0^{\circ})_2/(\pm 66^{\circ})_3/0^{\circ}]_s$ lamina lay-up.

Effect of loading path

Due to the experimental difficulties in controlling loading paths most of the biaxial experiments reported in the literature on tubular specimens have been conducted under proportional loading conditions. Since the strength anisotropy is inherently associated with unidirectional and multilayer fiber composites, load path dependent failure is expected. The load path effect on leakage behavior of composite vessels under a combined axial loading and internal pressure is shown in Fig. 5a. Six experiments were conducted to study path-dependent leakage

behavior of $[(\pm 66^\circ)_2/(0^\circ)_2/(\pm 66^\circ)_3/0^\circ]_s$ specimens. Typical loading sequences in these experiments are indicated in the figure. Stress biaxiality ratios of these experiments are selected to identify the possible load path dependency in three regimes: high axial load/internal pressure ratio, medium axial load/internal pressure ratio, and low axial load/internal pressure ratio. Results for each of these loading path dependent deformation and failure are compared with those of the proportional loading cases. These results indicated that the leakage strength difference among the cases with different loading paths is within the experimental scatter.

Figure 5: Effect of load path on E-glass/epoxy composite tubular vessels with $[(\pm 66^\circ)_2/(0^\circ)_2/(\pm 66^\circ)_3/0^\circ]_s$ lay-up a) failure envelope and b) deformations under various loading paths

The evolution of axial and transverse strains in the specimens under proportional and nonproportional loading paths are compared in Figure 5b. Obviously, the loading paths do not lead to a closed envelope in both stress and strain spaces. We also noted a difference between strain evolution under uniaxial (paths A and A') versus combined stress (paths B and B') loading paths. The facing paths (paths A and B) of the strain loading envelope are not parallel which indicates path-dependent strain evolution.

Leakage damage and failure mechanisms

Depending on the load biaxiality and laminate lay-up sequence, several leakage modes are observed. For the $[(\pm 55^\circ)]_2$ case, high axial/low internal pressure loading resulted in structural disintegration of the specimens, whereas a combined high internal pressure/low axial loading resulted in burst failure. Leakage failure for the $[(\pm 66^\circ)_2/(0^\circ)_2/(\pm 66^\circ)_3/0^\circ]_s$ case is in the form of weeping for all biaxial loading combinations considered in this study.

Detailed microscopy studies revealed that the inhomogeneous microstructure in a multilayer glass/epoxy laminate contained very complicated leakage paths. Formation of the leakage paths is found to be a consequence of progressive matrix cracking in the individual laminates. For example, the 0° plies of the $[(\pm 66^\circ)_2/(0^\circ)_2/(\pm 66^\circ)_3/0^\circ]_s$ vessels cracked earlier than the $\pm 66^\circ$ plies under a high internal pressure/low axial loading combination. While progressive damage evolution may lead to formation of a network of microcracks in the 0° plies, the $\pm 66^\circ$ plies acted as barrier to the leakage. Upon formation of microcracks in the $\pm 66^\circ$ plies, a through-the-thickness crack path lead to the weeping failure. In contrast, in high axial/low internal pressure loading

combinations, 0° plies formed a barrier to leakage, while the $\pm 66^\circ$ plies failed first. A typical micrograph of the leakage path is presented in Fig. 6.

Figure 6: Leakage path in a $[(\pm 66^\circ)_2/(0^\circ)_2/(\pm 66^\circ)_3/0^\circ]_s$ glass/epoxy composite under a combined internal pressure and low axial loading (Nonproportional loading experiments 1/0+0/1).

SUMMARY

An experimental study on the leakage failure of E-glass-fiber reinforced epoxy composite tubular vessels subjected to a combined internal pressure and axial loading has been conducted. The study required the development of an experiment facility, which involved a major effort to establish a multiaxial loading system with associated control units, an accurate leakage detection system, and a computer aided data acquisition and analysis system. Also, the design and construction of the specimens, the gripping system, the multiaxial extensometers, and other monitor/sensor devices were extremely involved as compared with the common simple uniaxial mechanical experimental systems. The results revealed important load-deformation characteristics of the composite vessels subjected to multiaxial loading. Leakage criteria and associated failure envelopes were determined for two important composite systems used in petroleum exploration and production operations. Better understanding of the leakage process in multilayer composite laminates has been gained by studying the damage growth and failure modes under combined axial loading and internal pressure. The important issues of stress biaxiality ratio and load path effects on composite leakage failure are addressed.

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